

Table 1. Resistance spectrum (%) of San-Huang-Zhan No. 2 from 1985 to 1995 in Guangdong, China.

Year	1985	1986	1987	1989	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995
RS	100	100	98	95	96.5	98	98	98	99.5

Table 2. Qualitative and quantitative resistances of San-Huang-Zhan No. 2 (SHZ).

Cultivar	Resistance spectrum (%)		LD (lesions cm ⁻¹)		LS (mm)		DLA (%)		Field observation			
	Guangdong ^a	China ^b	OD ^c	RV ^d	OD	RV	OD	RV	LB ^e		PB ^f	
									Mean	Maximum	Mean	Maximum
SHZ	99.5	95.2	0.3	4	1.3	19	8.5	10	1.3	4	1	3
IR36 (check)	58.2	-	0.4	6	1.4	20	24.6	30	3.0	9	3.2	9
B40 (check)	-	-	6.6	100	6.9	100	82.0	100	-	-	-	-

^aIncluding 220 isolates in Guangdong. ^bIncluding 124 isolates in China. ^cOD = observed data = mean of three experiments with 6 replications. ^dRV = relative value = tested data of cultivar/tested data of B40 × 100. ^eLB = leaf blast. ^fPB = panicle blast.

Table 3. Reaction to ZB13 blast isolate of F₁ and F₂ plants from crosses of San-Huang-Zhan No. 2 (SHZ).

Cross	F ₁ reaction	F ₂ reaction			χ ²	P
		R ^a	S	Expected ratio		
CO 39/SHZ	R	331	10	63:1	3.31	0.05-0.1
B40/SHZ	R	228	8	63:1	0.54	0.25-0.5
SHZ/CO 39	R	401	0			
SHZ/B40	R	601	0			

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

exhibited a wide qualitative RS and a high quantitative resistance for three factors—LD, LS, and DLA—whereas IR36 appeared to have a narrow qualitative RS but high quantitative resistance under a wide range of populations of *P. grisea* in different latitudes of China. Quantitative resistance plays a key role in the durability of resistance.

The genetic experiment showed that three independently dominant genes control the blast resistance of SHZ and there is another gene present in the cytoplasm of SHZ as well (Table 3).

IR36 represents an indica variety with durable blast resistance under tropical irrigated conditions. Some researchers concluded that the partial resistance of IR36 is associated with blast durability. Other researchers showed that IR36 had at least three major genes for complete resistance to two Philippine blast isolates. The inheritance of partial blast resistance in IR36 is most likely polygenic. SHZ seemed to have three major genes for complete resistance to blast, but some questions remain. Is the durability of SHZ in China mainly due to major genes or not? What is the function of another gene present in the cytoplasm for blast durability? Further research is needed to answer these questions. ■

Multilocational evaluation of promising advanced breeding lines for resistance to rice tungro viruses

R. C. Cabunagan, E. R. Angeles, E. R. Tiongco (current address: Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija), S. Villareal, O. Azzam, P. S. Teng, and G. S. Khush, IRRI; T. C. B. Chancellor, Natural Resources Institute, University of Greenwich, U.K.; X. H. Truong and S. Mancao, Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines; I.G.N. Astika, Food Crop Protection Centre VII, Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia; A. Muis, Maros Research Institute for Maize and Other Cereal Crops, Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia; A. K. Chowdhury, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya University, Kalyani, West Bengal, India; T. Ganapathy and N. Subra-

manian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

An important objective of IRRI's breeding program for irrigated rice ecosystems is to develop varieties with resistance to rice tungro viruses in order to achieve durable resistance to tungro disease. We conducted this study to monitor tungro virus and leafhopper vector variability between test locations, based on the reaction of selected varieties and advanced breeding lines with different sources of resistance. The advanced breeding lines were IR68305-18-1 (IR64*4/Balimau Putih); IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2 (IR1561-228-3-3*3/*Oryza longistaminata*); IR69705-1-1-3-2-1 (IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Merah);

IR71030-2-3-2-1 (IR1561-228-3-3*6/ARC11554). IR64 was used as a susceptible check and IR62 as a vector-resistant check with field resistance to tungro.

The table shows locations, seasons, and years of tests. At each location, we used a randomized complete block design with four replications. The plot size was 8 m × 8 m with 2 m between plots. We transplanted 21-d-old seedlings at 20 cm × 20 cm spacing, with 2-3 seedlings hill⁻¹. The plants were exposed to natural infection with tungro viruses in the field. We assessed plants for disease symptoms and sampled leaves to detect tungro viruses by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) at 30-35 and 55-60 d after transplanting (DAT). We recorded

Average^a percentage infection with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), visual disease incidence, and number of green leafhoppers (GLH) in different varieties and advanced breeding lines planted in field trials in the Philippines, Indonesia, and India in 1995-96.

Test location/season	Varieties/lines	Infection (%)			GLH (no.) ^c
		BB ^b	SS	Visual	
<i>Philippines</i>					
Maligaya,	IR62	0.8	34.2	0.3	24.6
Nueva Ecija	IR64	27.0	67.3	23.1	169.5
1995 WS ^d , 1996 WS	IR68305-18-1	2.0	55.2	0.1	145.4
	IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2	0.9	28.5	0.1	134.8
	IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	2.3	3.4	0.2	174.8
	IR71030-2-3-2-1	0.6	11.1	0.1	52.1
Midsayap,	IR62	8.9	48.8	17.8	10.2
North Cotabato	IR64	80.8	89.1	92.2	100.7
1995 WS, 1996 DS, 1996 WS	IR68305-18-1	18.0	72.3	21.2	42.0
	IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2	38.8	74.1	41.6	44.8
	IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	6.4	6.0	1.8	35.1
	IR71030-2-3-2-1	6.1	13.4	20.9	12.8
<i>Indonesia</i>					
Celuk,	IR62	3.8	9.1	2.9	2.0
Bali	IR64	48.0	64.8	64.2	5.6
1995 DS, 1996 WS	IR68305-18-1	18.2	41.4	15.3	1.4
	IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2	29.7	52.1	31.3	5.2
	IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	3.7	2.0	1.2	2.7
	IR71030-2-3-2-1	1.8	4.4	0.7	1.5
Maros,	IR62	3.3	6.1	0.6	10.4
South Sulawesi	IR64	8.2	13.4	3.5	15.2
1995 DS, 1996 WS	IR68305-18-1	2.2	5.8	0.2	14.1
	IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2	3.4	5.6	0.2	13.8
	IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	4.4	4.3	0.0	11.0
	IR71030-2-3-2-1	2.2	2.6	0.0	12.0
<i>India</i>					
Chakdaha,	IR62	1.5	7.8	9.8	26.6
West Bengal	IR64	4.3	18.0	20.0	27.9
1996 WS	IR68305-18-1	1.1	5.1	10.8	35.9
	IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2	0.8	6.0	23.8	20.5
	IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	0.3	1.1	9.5	24.9
	IR71030-2-3-2-1	6.1	31.1	16.9	26.0
Tirur,	IR62	2.3	14.5	2.5	10.4
Tamil Nadu	IR64	10.0	24.9	16.8	11.3
1996 DS, 1996 WS	IR68305-18-1	1.1	14.0	2.2	14.4
	IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2	1.4	16.6	2.2	10.0
	IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	0.6	8.6	2.3	15.1
	IR71030-2-3-2-1	5.9	15.8	7.7	12.4

^aAverage across all seasons and computed from the mean of two samplings at 30-35 and 55-60 d after transplanting. ^bBB = total RTBV from BS and B alone, SS = total RTSV from BS and S alone. Infection with tungro viruses was assessed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, visual incidence was assessed based on characteristic tungro symptoms of stunting and yellowing. ^cCount based on 10 sweeps of a 30-cm-diameter insect net in each plot. ^dWS = wet season, DS = dry season.

disease and sampled leaves in six quadrats of 4 × 4 hills arranged in a “W” pattern in each plot. We collected vector leafhoppers using 10 sweeps of a 30-cm-diameter insect net in each plot on the same dates as for recording disease.

Tungro disease incidence was low in Maros, Indonesia, as evidenced by the reaction of IR64, but was high enough at all other locations to allow the per-

formance of the test entries to be evaluated effectively (see table). Tungro incidence was the highest in Celuk, Indonesia, and Midsayap, Philippines. Locational differences in the reaction of the test lines and varieties were observed only in IR71030-2-3-2-1, which had a relatively high infection with tungro viruses both in Chakdaha and Tirur, India, compared with other locations (see table).

The figure shows the average reactions of the test lines and varieties, regardless of test location and season. Infection with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) was the lowest in IR69705-1-1-3-2-1, IR71030-2-3-2-1, and IR62 at 3-4%. In contrast, a mean RTBV infection of 16% was recorded in IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2. Mean infection with rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) was the lowest in IR69705-1-1-3-2-1 and IR71030-2-3-2-1 at 5% and 12%, respectively. RTSV infection in IR71026-3-2-4-3-5-2 and IR68305-18-1 was 36% and 38%, respectively. Tungro incidence scored visually was 2% in IR69705-1-1-3-2-1 and was less than 10% in IR62, IR71030-2-3-2-1, and IR68305-18-1 (see figure). Tungro incidence on the susceptible check, IR64, was 44%. Green leafhopper numbers were the lowest on IR62 and IR71030-2-3-2-1 and were similar to those on the susceptible IR64 on the other lines.

The most promising advanced breeding line was IR69705-1-1-3-2-1, which showed tolerance for RTBV and resistance to RTSV at all test locations. This indicates that the virus resistance was successfully transferred from its parent, Utri Merah, and that this resistance is likely to be effective against tungro disease at a wide range of locations. IR71030-2-3-2-1 showed resistance to both RTBV and RTSV at most sites, but infection was relatively high in Chakdaha and Tirur. The virus-resistant parent of this line, ARC11554, originates from India. Further evaluation needs to be done to confirm the results. ■

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Mean tungro disease incidence (□), infection with rice tungro bacilliform (▨) and spherical (■) viruses, and number of green leafhoppers (▩) per 10 sweeps of a 30-cm-diameter insect net in advanced breeding lines and varieties at six locations in India, Indonesia, and the Philippines in replicated field trials in 1995 and 1996.

Pest resistance

Advanced breeding lines with resistance to rice tungro viruses

E. R. Angeles, R. C. Cabunagan, E. R. Tiongco (presently with Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Nueva Ecija, Philippines), O. Azzam, P. S. Teng, and G. S. Khush, IRRI, and T. C. B. Chancellor, Natural Resources Institute, UK

Some 139 advanced breeding lines with improved agronomic characters derived from crosses involving tungro-resistant rice varieties were evaluated for resistance to rice tungro viruses under greenhouse conditions. These lines consistently showed a resistant reaction to tungro under natural field infection in the tungro nursery at IRRI for at least six growing seasons. In the crosses, Utri Rajapan, Utri Merah, ARC11554,

Habiganj DW8, and wild rices *Oryza longistaminata* and *O. rufipogon* (accession no. 105908 and 105910 and one with an unknown accession no.) were used as sources of resistance to tungro, whereas IR1561-228-3-3, IR24, and IR64 were used as the recurrent parents. Except for ARC11554, *O. longistaminata*, IR24, and IR64, all the other parents are susceptible to the virus vector green leafhopper (GLH).

The breeding lines were tested for tungro reaction using the forced-inoculation method. Some or 30-40 seven-day-old seedlings of each breeding line were inoculated with the virus for 24 h in test tubes using three viruliferous GLH, *Nepho-tettix virescens* (Distant), fed for 4 d on plants infected with rice tungro bacilli-form virus (RTBV) and

rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). After inoculation, the seedlings were planted in clay pots at 10 seedlings pot⁻¹ and maintained for 1 mo inside insect-proof enclosures in the greenhouse. Leaf samples were collected from each plant and tested by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). In the 1995 dry-season test, inoculated seedlings of the test lines were transplanted in the field after leaf sampling to further subject the materials to natural infection. Each of the lines was planted in 2 rows of inoculated seedlings, with 20 hills row⁻¹. One month after transplanting, leaf samples were again collected from each plant and tested by ELISA.

Only 94 of the breeding lines tested were confirmed to have resistance to tungro. Of these, 4 showed resistance to both RTBV and RTSV, whereas the other 90 breeding lines showed resistance to RTSV only (Table 1). Two breeding lines each from the crosses involving *O. rufipogon* (accession no. 105910) and Habiganj DW8 were resistant to both RTBV and RTSV, whereas breeding lines derived from crosses involving the other parents showed resistance to RTSV only. Progenies of *O. rufipogon*, Utri Merah, and Utri Rajapan were among the lines that exhibited a high level of resistance to RTSV.

An increase in RTBV and RTSV infection was observed in most of the breeding lines when inoculated seedlings of the test materials were transplanted in the field and further exposed to natural infection (Table 2). Breeding lines from Utri Merah and Utri Rajapan crosses, however, showed a decrease in RTBV infection even after further exposure to natural infection. Utri Merah is known to have resistance to the multiplication of RTBV and the decrease in RTBV detected in these breeding lines is presumed to be due to a decrease in virus titre in the infected plants.

Some of the most promising breeding lines from the crosses tested in these trials were selected for further evaluation in areas with high tungro incidence. These breeding lines are now being tested in replicated field trials in India, Indonesia, and the Philippines. ■